

The Thesmophorion of Pella

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The Thesmophorion of Pella, the capital of the Macedonian kingdom, was discovered in 1980. The structure is round in shape. Given its raw construction, it was, probably, built underground. There are twenty holes, of uneven shape and size, carved into the ground, probably the place where the libations to Demeter and her daughter were performed. A rectangular structure, identified as an altar, made of clay and gravels, was erected at the center of the structure. Many votive offerings (most of them figurines) along with animal bones seashell and burnt material were found around and onto the altar.

Date Range: 400 BCE - 100 CE

Region: Pella

Region tags: Greece, Macedonia

Pella served as the capital of the ancient Greek kingdom of Macedon.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Lilimpaki- Akamati 1996: Lilimpaki-Akamati, M. Το Θεσμοφόριο της Πέλλας, Athens 1996.
- Source 2: Lilimpaki-Akamati 1993: Lilimpaki- Akamati, M. “Θεσμοφόρια στη Μακεδονία” Ancient Masedonia V. Papers read at the Fifth Interanational Symposium held in Thessaloniki, October 10-15, 1989, Thessaloniki 1993, 809-819.
- Source 3: Maniataki 2018: Τα Ιερά και οι λατρείες της Αρχαίας Πέλλας κατά την Κλασική και Ελληνιστική περίοδο. Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Unpublished Master Thesis.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.pella-museum.gr/explore/museum/enotita3/thriskeia-latries>
- Source 1 Description: Official Page of the Archaeological Museum of Pella
- Source 2 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/gh251.jsp?obj_id=13601
- Source 2 Description: Official Page of the Ministry of Culture

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1980

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Ephorate of Antiquities

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: It is located at the northeast edge of the ancient city or outside the city walls. Perhaps, it was placed close to a gate of the fortification walls, providing better access to the inhabitants

of Pella.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: It is located at the northeast edge of the ancient city or outside the city walls. Perhaps, it was placed close to a gate of the fortification walls, providing better access to the inhabitants of Pella.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Circular

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: No

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: A temple and stoas might have existed, but there is no trace of them.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Individual

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The figurines and the artefacts suggest that was used for at least two centuries.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The altar seems to have been used and repaired many times as the multiple layers of clay with which it had been coated, suggest. Perhaps, the votive offerings dedicated each year were being embedded onto the altar.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Demeter and Kore. There are also figurines of Athena, Artemis, Eros, Nike, Hercules, Dionysus, Pan.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

- Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

- No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

- Yes

Notes: There was not only one structure. The round-shaped structured that has been excavated hosted a rectangular altar. These two were probably part of a complex that included a stoa or a temple.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

- No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

- Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

- Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

- Field doesn't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Only the foundation of the construction has been preserved.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 78.5

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: In different areas of the pavement, twenty holes, of uneven shape and size, are carved into the ground. Those underground holes turned out to be the megara, the place where the libations to Demeter and her daughter were performed.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

Notes: The interior of the walls was coated with a mixture of clay and fodder enforced with rooftiles' fragments, that have been partly preserved in situ.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It was probably local.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Notes: White and yellow plaster has been found.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

Notes: It is probable that wood was used for the construction, especially for supporting the roof but it has not been preserved.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass

– Field doesn't know

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: The stones were carved into blocks, clay was used for coating the walls and roof tiles were constructed.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Notes: Probably yes but the state of conservation does not allow us to understand much on that subject.

↳ On the outside:

– Field doesn't know

↳ On the inside:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Probably yes but it is mainly the clay figurines that have been found during the excavation.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Figurines representing or bearing features resembling Demeter, Kore, Athena, Artemis, Nike, Hercules, Dionysos, Pan, Hermes, Hades have been found.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There are many figurines of pigs, a common votive offering in the sanctuaries of Demeter as the sacrifice of a pig was a necessary act during the Thesmophoria.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Notes: Probably yes but no statue has survived.

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: Probably yes but no statue has survived.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Probably yes but no statue has survived.

↳ Statues of humans:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: Probably yes but no relief has survived.

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Probably yes but no statue has survived.

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably yes but no inscription has survived.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Demeter is represented in a frontal posture and she wears a polos on her head. Athena is depicted with bull-horns as protector of the livestock.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: It is probable that the episode of the abduction of Persephone is represented at the sanctuary.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: Probably yes, even though these statues have not survived.

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– Yes [specify]: In different areas of the pavement, twenty holes, of uneven shape and size, are carved into the ground. Those underground holes turned out to be the megara, the place where the libations to Demeter and her daughter were performed.

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: Animal bones, mainly porcine and mutton, and seashell were found.

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: Animal bones, mainly porcine and mutton, and seashell were found. Sacrifice of pigs was a common rite during the Thesmophoria.

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Daily life objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The feeling of having a reciprocal relation is very important.

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: The sacrifice of a pig is a necessary act during the Thesmophoria. For that reason they also offered figurines of pigs. In addition, mutton bones have been found.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: The objects found in the premises of the sanctuary present a large variety, composed of figurines, vases, metallic and glass artifacts.

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: There was the altar for the sacrifices, the "megara" that accepted the libations but probably also other structures around the circular building that served these purposes.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

–specify: Annual

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

–Only initiates

–Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The Thesmophoria was a festivity addressed to women that celebrated fertility and nature.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The circular shape of the building, the place of the altar, the holes-"megara" for the libations are all construction elements defined by the rites and festivals performed there.

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Field doesn't know

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: Field doesn't know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably yes.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The building where the religious specialists would have lived has not been found in the excavations but it is something that would be expected.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Thesmophorion of Pella, Lilimpaki-Akamati, Maria. Το Θεσμοφόριο Της Πέλλας. Athens, 1996.

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